

SPECIFIC QUALITIES OF IMPROVING THE PEDAGOGICAL MECHANISMS FOR THE DEVELOPMENT OF PROFESSIONAL COMPETENCE OF FUTURE ENGINEERS.

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Abstract: Currently, it covers issues such as improving pedagogical mechanisms for developing the professional competence of future engineers and raising personnel training to the level of current requirements, creating a relationship-based mechanism for improving the quality of education, improving its content, and forming new attitudes and views among students to the educational process. In the years of independence, a new system of personnel training was created in our republic, highly qualified, competitive, able to work independently in the chosen field of study, meeting the modern requirements for the quality of specialists, able to make a worthy contribution to the scientific-technical, socio-economic and cultural development of the country, rapidly advancing socio-economic the training of specialists who can adapt to the conditions of development and have high cultural, spiritual and moral qualities is being carried out consistently.

Keywords: Competence, professional competence, qualities of professional competence, pedagogical professional competence, pedagogical mechanisms, engineers.

Specific qualities of improving the pedagogical mechanisms for the development of professional competence of future engineers study of pedagogical,

psychological, and scientific-technical literature on the subject; questionnaire to determine students' knowledge and understanding of research activities; interviews with students to determine their assessment of the formation of research skills; monitoring students' performance in laboratory work; interview; monitoring the process of students using modern didactic tools; statistical and analytical analysis and processing of the results of pedagogical experiments. A teacher must be able to highlight the qualities of his competence. In this place, we will talk about these and related ideas.

The English concept of "competence" literally means "ability". The content shows "the effective use of theoretical knowledge in the activity, the ability to demonstrate high-level professional skills, skills, and talent" and has its quality [1].

Speaking about competence, it entered the field of education as a result of psychological research. That's why competence is "How a specialist behaves in any unconventional situations, unexpected situations, starts communication, takes a new way in relations with opponents, performs ambiguous tasks, uses information full of contradictions, consistently develops "ownership of a plan of action in progressive and complex processes". This is very important for the topic of improving the pedagogical mechanisms for the development of the professional competence of future engineers.

Professional competence is the concept of the acquisition of knowledge, skills, and abilities necessary for carrying out professional activity by a specialist and their practical application at a high level. Professional competence does not mean the acquisition of separate knowledge and skills by a specialist, but the acquisition of integrative knowledge and actions in each independent direction. Also, competence requires constant enrichment of professional knowledge, learning new information, understanding important social requirements, finding new information, processing it, and being able to use it in one's work [2].

To develop the professional competence of future engineers, to determine the basics and principles of the technology of creating and applying modern didactic

tools in the development of the professional competence of students of technical higher education institutions, to determine their general structure and specific characteristics, to use cloud technologies in classes to develop the professional competence of students of technical higher educational institutions.

The essence of the qualities reflected based on professional competence is briefly explained.

1. Social competence - the ability to show activity in social relations, and the ability to communicate with subjects in professional activities.

2. Special competence - preparation for organizing professional-pedagogical activities, rational solution of professional-pedagogical tasks, realistic assessment of activity results, consistent development of BKM, based on this competence psychological, methodical, informational, creative, innovative, and communicative competence is noticeable. They contain the following content:

1) psychological competence - the ability to create a healthy psychological environment in the pedagogical process, to organize positive communication with students and other participants of the educational process, to be able to understand and eliminate various negative psychological conflicts in time;

2) methodical competence - the methodical rational organization of the pedagogical process, the correct determination of the forms of educational or educational activity, the ability to choose methods and tools under the purpose, the ability to effectively use methods, the successful use of tools;

3) information competence - searching for, collecting, sorting, and processing necessary, important, necessary, and useful information in the information environment and using it purposefully, appropriately, and effectively;

4) creative competence - a critical, creative approach to pedagogical activities, the ability to demonstrate one's creative skills;

- 5) innovative competence - putting forward new ideas on improving the pedagogical process, improving the quality of education, increasing the effectiveness of the educational process, and effectively implementing them into practice;
 - 6) communicative competence - the ability to communicate sincerely with all participants of the educational process, including students, to be able to listen to them, and to have a positive influence on them.
3. Personal competence - achieving consistent professional growth, increasing the level of qualification, to demonstrate one's internal capabilities in professional activity.
 4. Technological competence - mastering advanced technologies that enrich professional and pedagogical BCM, being able to use modern tools, techniques, and technologies [3].
 5. Extreme competence - the ability to make rational decisions and act correctly in emergencies (natural disasters, technological process failure), when pedagogical conflicts arise.

This system is a structure aimed at the development of the professional competence of future engineers, it helps to contribute to the self-awareness of engineers, the ability to think broadly, the improvement of pedagogical mechanisms, and sincere communication.

Working on oneself and self-development are important in acquiring professional and pedagogical competence. Self-development tasks are determined through self-analysis and self-assessment. To gain professional competence, a pedagogue should pay attention to consistent self-development. The "Individual development program" is useful for the pedagogue in self-development. After all, in this program, the qualities of competence that a pedagogue has and the quality that needs to be developed.

Therefore, the need to withstand strong competition in the labor market in the conditions of market relations encourages each specialist to develop professional competence and qualities specific to him. The basis of competence means "ability"

in terms of vocabulary, and "effective use of theoretical knowledge in activity, ability to demonstrate high-level professional skills, skills, and talent" in terms of content, social, special (psychological, methodical, informational, creative, innovative and communicative), such qualities as personal, technological and extreme competence are reflected.

References:

1. Markova A.K. Psixologiya professionalizma. – M.: Znanie, 1996.
2. Muslimov N.A. Bo‘lajak kasb ta’limi o‘qituvchilarini kasbiy shakllantirish / Monografiya. – T.: Fan, 2004.
3. Muslimov N.A., va boshqalar. Kasb ta’limi o‘qituvchilarining kasbiy kompetentligini shakllantirish texnologiyasi/ Monografiya. – T.: “Fan va texnologiya” nashriyoti, 2013.